

THE ROLE OF CULTURE, ART AND MASS MEDIA IN ENSURING THE SPIRITUAL WELL-BEING OF YOUNG PEOPLE

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ABSTRACT

This article highlights the role of culture, art, and mass media in shaping the moral development of young people. It explains how culture helps to adopt national values and historical traditions, how art fosters aesthetic taste and spiritual growth, and how mass media delivers useful information. The article is illustrated with examples and encourages youth to develop morally.

Article Introduction: Explaining what spiritual perfection is Every person should strive not only for knowledge, but also for spiritual and moral maturity in life. When a person has a pure heart, a clear mind, and perfect behavior, he achieves true perfection. Spiritual perfection is the manifestation of the most beautiful and strong sides of the human spirit, the harmony of the heart and mind, and the perfection of behavior and qualities. This not only makes a person a person who knows himself and can distinguish between good and evil, but also helps him become a responsible and kind person who is respected in society.

The main signs of spiritual perfection are: 1) self-knowledge and the ability to analyze himself; 2) the ability to distinguish between good and evil; 3) respect for moral values: justice, honesty, kindness, patience; 4) the desire to be useful to society; 5) inner peace and spiritual stability.

A spiritually mature person plays an important role in the positive development of society.

He will be far from violence, betrayal and wrong decisions.

He will also achieve success and peace in his personal life.

Main Idea and Purpose of the Article:

The spiritual maturity of young people is the basis for the healthy and sustainable development of society. Spiritual maturity means a person's moral, spiritual, intellectual and cultural maturity, the ability to distinguish between good and evil.

This article highlights the role of culture, art and the media in shaping the spiritual maturity of young people. The importance of mastering national values and historical traditions through culture, aesthetic taste and spiritual development through art, and the importance of conveying useful information through the media are explained with examples. The purpose of the article is to encourage young people to be spiritually mature.

The role of culture

Culture is one of the most important tools in the spiritual and moral development of a person. Through culture, young people learn national values, historical traditions, and positive norms of behavior of society.

Key aspects:

1. Teaches national values: Culture introduces young people to their nation, history, and traditions. Through this, they develop qualities such as patriotism and respect.
2. Provides spiritual and moral education: Books, theater, music, and cinema form the emotions, aesthetic taste, and ability to make moral decisions of young people.
3. Teaches harmony with society: Cultural values encourage young people to treat people around them with respect and responsibility.

The role of art

Art has a strong influence on the spiritual and moral development of young people. Through music, painting, theater, cinema and other forms of art, a person develops aesthetic taste, feelings and the ability to make moral decisions. Through historical and artistic works, qualities such as patriotism, friendship, honesty and responsibility are instilled in the minds of young people. Through painting, musical performance or theater, young people learn to appreciate beauty and express their thoughts through art. Art awakens the emotions of young people, educates them as patient, loving and creative individuals.

The role of the media

The media - the Internet, television, radio and social networks - are important tools in the moral and spiritual development of young people. Through them, they provide useful information, increase knowledge and instill positive values. The media introduces young people to history, science, culture and art. Through TV programs, social networks and journalistic materials, values such as friendship, honesty, respect and responsibility are instilled in the minds of young people. Useful and spiritual content through the media encourages young people to think positively and choose a healthy lifestyle. Educational TV shows, cultural blogs and Internet projects introduce young people to their values, help them to consciously respond to social problems.

Conclusion

The spiritual well-being of young people is an important factor for the healthy and sustainable development of society. A spiritually mature person is a person who is mature in his or her morals, spiritual state, knowledge and culture, and who can contribute to positive changes in society. As shown in the article, culture, art and the media are important complementary tools in the spiritual development of young people. Culture introduces young people to national values, history and traditions, instills moral and social values. Art, on the other hand, encourages young people to think creatively and develop good qualities through aesthetic taste and emotional education. The mass media, on the other hand, serve to develop young people morally, intellectually and spiritually by providing useful information through modern technologies and social networks. Therefore, culture, art and the media together are effective tools in forming the spiritual development of young people. They teach young people to value positive qualities such as honesty, loyalty, respect, patriotism and friendship, and encourage them to make responsible decisions in their personal and social lives. As a result,

young people are formed as well-rounded individuals who are useful not only for their own lives, but also for the development of people around them and society. Thus, the harmonious functioning of culture, art and the media is an important foundation for ensuring the spiritual well-being of young people, creating an opportunity to educate the future generation as spiritually mature and useful individuals to society..

References:

1. Abdug'aniyev, A. (2018). Ma'naviyat va shaxs tarbiyasi. Toshkent: O'zbekiston milliy universiteti nashriyoti.
2. Islomov, S. (2020). Madaniyat va yoshlar tarbiyasi. Toshkent: Fan va texnologiya.
3. Karimova, N. (2019). San'at va ma'naviy rivojlanish. Toshkent: Adabiyot nashriyoti.
4. Rasulov, D. (2021). Ommaviy axborot vositalarining ijtimoiy ahamiyati. Toshkent: Ilm-fan.
5. Toshpulatov, M. (2017). Yoshlar tarbiyasida madaniyat va san'atning roli. Samarqand: Samarqand davlat universiteti nashriyoti.
6. Internet manbalar:
www.unesco.org – Culture and Education for Youth Development
www.uzdaily.uz – OAV va yoshlar tarbiyasi haqida maqolalar